

Structural model of family functioning, psychological capital, psychologically active psychological needs: the mediating role of adolescent responsibility in adolescence

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Background: Responsible behavior is one of the indicators of a healthy human and its strengthening and growth will not be possible except by identifying the factors affecting responsible behavior. To this end, the present study seeks to answer the question of whether family performance, psychological capital and satisfaction of psychological needs of adolescents influence their level of responsibility and mental vitality or not? **Aims:** The present study was conducted with the aim of family performance, psychological capital, psychological needs with mental vitality: the mediating role of adolescents' responsibility during adolescence. **Methods:** The present study was descriptive, with correlation and structural equations. The statistical population of this study consisted of all adolescents aged 14 to 18 years in Tehran in 1399.

The research sample was 400 adolescents in districts 1 and 2 of Tehran who were selected by multi-stage cluster sampling. Research data was collected using the self-report questionnaire of Kim and Kim family (2007), psychological needs of Lagourdia et al. (2002), McGee (2011), Soroush (2012) and the mental vitality of Kiyez et al. 2003). Data were analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient and structural equation modeling. **Results:** The findings showed that family performance, psychological needs, and psychological capital have a direct and indirect positive effect on students' responsibility and mental vitality. The results of structural equation modeling showed that 39% of the variance of responsibility and 48% of the variance of mental vitality are explained by family performance, psychological needs and psychological capital and responsibility. **Conclusion:** Recognizing the factors affecting students' responsibility and mental vitality provides the possibility of anticipation and planning to help ensure their mental health. It is also possible to take steps to increase social, emotional, and psychological vitality by creating a suitable environment in schools.

Keywords:

family performance, psychological needs, psychological capital and responsibility, mental vitality, students